

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.72 Max: 63.002	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1469 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 2145-2149		Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 335
DEFINITION intermediate wall between 1183+ 1393			Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1327	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic <input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		Geological <input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		Organic <input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
				Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit						
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1327			Covers:			
Is cut by: 1347 (grave)			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS dry, sunny conditions SU is still in situ						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: South central in Area B 204 Shape: long rectangular not excavated in 204						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: (Site) N-S

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) 5-7 cm Medium (range) 10-17 cm Large (range) 30-35 cm Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing: NONE

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: length 100 cm, width 40 cm, height (as in section) 45 cm

Description: Partial wall of irregular tufo stones + large tile fragments. The wall is cut to the south by a grave (cut SU 1437); beyond this the wall seems to continue on the same alignment as SU 1393. The wall is also aligned with wall SU 1183 to the north, of ashlar tufo blocks.

INTERPRETATION

Truncated wall, made of opus mixtum with a high amount of tile fragments. Wall is aligned with SU 1183 and SU 1393

SOIL SAMPLING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):	NON SOIL SAMPLES: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:	SIEVING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):
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STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Filled-out by	CHM JSARR	on	1.8.2011	3.8.11
	Revised by	CHM	on	3.8.2011	
	PDFd by	ELR	on	3.8.2011	
	Entered by		on		